

Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado **Boulder**

Team Science Related Training Courses

By Kayleigh Ward, ESIIL | May 6th, 2026

The ESIIL Team Science team has curated some of the available training courses related to team science that may be of interest to students, new collaborators and others organizing teams. Despite the wide application of team science today there remains a gap in terms of accessible courses and the application of team science courses (e.g., business, medical, science, etc). This gap is especially important when trying to socialize and train the next generation of team science practitioners and scientists within SciTS.

As a result, we have endeavored to provide a (non-exhaustive) list of training courses to the best of our ability that are free (or limited cost) and that cover a variety of skills, disciplines and environments. We have also included some items that may be free to students through their institutional affiliation. In previous resource documents, we already covered toolkits and books, so here we specifically focus on courses. To the extent possible we tried to retrieve both generalist team science related courses (i.e., skills development) along with a core pillar of team science—clinical and translational science courses. We have also tried to avoid courses that are specific to company employee training programs, employee management or about business management.

The trainings we pulled are of value both to students and junior and senior principal investigators. For PIs who have never had formal leadership training or training on how to facilitate a positive and productive team environment, some of these trainings may be a useful way to enhance your leadership, communication, coordination and team-care skills. Fortunately, most of these courses require minimal time commitments.

Important disclaimers

The listed tables below separate confirmed free/open offerings from adjacent massive open online course (MOOC-style) options and other relevant offerings. We include the name of the course, its provider, a currently accessible link, what the modality or learning format is, the level of the course (intro, inter, adv), who it is the best fit for, and if listed by the course provider, a synopsis of learning objectives. As we have not taken these courses we cannot verify the quality of them, but nonetheless they may be of value to anyone looking to dive into skills and competencies related to team science. Neither ESIIL nor the Team Science team have any affiliation with Coursera, EdX or FutureLearn. Happy learning!

Free online and open courses

Course	Provider	URL	Format	Level	Audience	Objectives
Intro to The Science of Team Science	Duke CTSI / TRECC	https://sites.duke.edu/trec/c/team-science/	Self-paced, online via Canvas***	Intro	Students and learners new to clinical/translational research	Recognize the value of team science; explain the Science of Team Science; understand cross-disciplinary collaboration in CTS settings

***While this class is hosted on Canvas, you do not need to be a Duke student to enroll. They have instructions for registering as a non-affiliate.

MOOC-style

Here we have listed some courses that may require an affiliate license to access for no-cost, or that may be provided at reduced cost to students. We have added a cost and duration column to clarify the potential money and time investment for these. Especially for Coursera you may be able to access these courses at little to no cost if you are located in the United States. If you are unsure and are a student, check to see if your institution has “Coursera for Campus.” Coursera does provide a first module preview too. EdX also has a large catalog of free courses as does FutureLearn (EU), although Coursera seems to have the largest catalog. We did look for courses offered in the EU under FutureLearn and they do offer a free tier that limits how quickly you can move through courses. If a course is not covered under their free tier, a single class is \$54 and does not require a subscription.

Course	Provider	URL	Cost	Format	Duration	Level	Audience	Objectives
Introduction to Translational Science	Coursera / University of Rochester	https://www.coursera.org/learn/intro-translational-science	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	1 week at 10 hours/week; 3 modules	Intro	Learners new to translational science; public health and medical students	Define translational science; explain barriers and stages from T1 to T4; understand CTSA context
Translating Research to Patients	Coursera / University of Michigan	https://www.coursera.org/learn/translating-research-to-patients	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	6 hours; 3 modules	Intro	Learners in clinical/translational research	Clinical research basics, trials, IRBs, ethics, and translation to patients
Translating Research to Communities	Coursera / University of Michigan	https://www.coursera.org/learn/translating-research-to-communities	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	7 hours; 3 modules	Intro	Learners needing community/public-health orientation	Population health, community inclusion, data ethics, and sharing research findings with communities

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Course	Provider	URL	Cost	Format	Duration	Level	Audience	Objectives
Collaborative Working in a Remote Team	FutureLearn / University of Leeds	https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/collaborative-working-in-a-remote-team	Free limited access	Scheduled short course with online access; not always offered	2 weeks, ~3 hours/week	Intro	Distributed teams and learners working remotely	Collaboration, remote teamwork, communication, and digital work practices
Online Interdisciplinary Learning Course	FutureLearn/ University of Leeds	https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/interdisciplinary-learning-working-across-disciplines	\$54.00	Scheduled short course with online access; not always offered	2 weeks	Intro	Academic researchers undertaking research in new areas or professionals working on projects with people from different disciplines.	Discover what interdisciplinary learning is; Discover strategies for working in an interdisciplinary environment.
Openness in Science and Innovation	FutureLearn/ Universitat Potsdam	https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/openness-in-science-and-innovation	Free limited access	Scheduled short course with online access; not always offered	8 weeks	Intro	Students and researchers who want to gain theoretical insights as well as practical skills in open science.	Discover the advantages of openness and gain skills to make research and innovation accessible, transparent, and collaborative.
The Arts and Science of Relationships: Understanding Human Needs	Coursera/ University of Toronto	https://www.coursera.org/learn/human-needs	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	3 weeks at 10 hours/week; 6 modules	Intro	Learners interested in interpersonal relationships; also relevant to social work/health-care contexts	Introduces SSLD concepts, needs/circumstances/characteristics/capacity assessment, relationship-management practice, communication, and relationship-building skills.
Team Success through Cultural Awareness Specialization	Coursera/ University of Colorado	https://www.coursera.org/specializations/culture-teamwork-diverse-workgroups	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	Specialization/3-course series; 12 weeks at 2 hours/week	Team experience	Professionals working in multicultural or diverse team settings	Build cultural agility, navigate cultural differences, improve cross-cultural communication, build inclusion, and strengthen team success.
The Neuroscience of Leading High-	Coursera/ University of	https://www.coursera.org/learn/the-neuroscience-of-	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	3 weeks at 10	Intro	Leaders, managers, coaches, and team leads interested in	Use neuroscience and psychology to understand motivation, goal setting,

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Course	Provider	URL	Cost	Format	Duration	Level	Audience	Objectives
Performance Teams	Colorado Boulder	leading-high-performance-teams			hours/week; 5 modules		motivation and team performance	storytelling, psychological safety, influence, collaboration, trust, and coaching.
The Power of Team Culture	Coursera/ University of Pennsylvania	https://www.coursera.org/learn/team-culture	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	8 hours; 5 modules	Intro	Team members and team leaders who want to understand culture's effect on performance	Recognize hidden aspects of team culture, understand ritual and symbols, and form, join, or lead teams more effectively.
Optimizing Diversity on Teams	Coursera/ University of Pennsylvania	https://www.coursera.org/learn/diverse-teams	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	10 hours; 4 modules	Intro	Team leaders, managers, and team members working with diverse teams	Use diversity to improve team performance, innovation, and creativity; draw out collective wisdom; handle conflict; reduce bias; and create inclusive team practices.
Cultivate Teamwork and Collaboration	Coursera/ Harvard Business Review	https://www.coursera.org/learn/cultivate-teamwork-and-collaboration	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	2 weeks at 10 hours/week; 3 modules	Inter	Leaders and managers responsible for team cohesion, collaboration, and performance	Build stronger teams, encourage collaboration, improve communication and feedback, support transitions, set goals, foster accountability, and manage global collaboration challenges.
Leading Teams	Coursera/ University of Michigan	https://www.coursera.org/learn/leading-teams	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	10 hours; 4 modules	Intro	Current or aspiring team leaders and team contributors	Build teams, improve teamwork and collaboration, establish roles and structures, manage decision-making, resolve conflict, build trust, and continuously improve team performance.
Communicating in Groups and Teams	Coursera/ Arizona State University	https://www.coursera.org/learn/communicating-in-groups-and-teams	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	10 hours; 7 modules	Intro	Learners who want clearer communication in	Set expectations, guide discussions, create productive team cultures,

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Course	Provider	URL	Cost	Format	Duration	Level	Audience	Objectives
		communicatinggroup sandteams					groups, team meetings, and collaborative settings	facilitate meetings, practice active listening, handle conflict, and give/receive feedback.
Team Communication	Coursera/ Arizona State University	https://www.coursera.org/learn/team-communication	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	5 hours; 6 modules	Intro	Team members, team leads, and workplace professionals who communicate in groups	Strengthen group communication strategies, feedback practices, productive team cultures, meeting facilitation, active listening, and conflict handling.
Leading Teams: Building Effective Team Cultures	Coursera/ University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign	https://www.coursera.org/learn/leading-teams-building-effective-team-cultures	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	10 hours; 4 modules	Intro	Team leaders, managers, and professionals shaping team culture	Understand team culture, connect psychological safety to performance, encourage collaboration and problem-solving, and build cultures of safety, engagement, and growth.
Creating a Team Culture of Continuous Learning	Coursera/ University of Pennsylvania	https://www.coursera.org/learn/continuous-learning-culture	Coursera monthly fee	Self-paced, flexible schedule	10 hours; 4 modules	Intro	Team leaders, managers, organizational-development learners, and teams trying to improve learning practices	Diagnose barriers to team learning, understand teams in organizational context, build continuous-learning habits, and create environments that support learning and innovation.

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